

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF HEXAMETHYLENEDIBIGUANIDE WITH METALLIC ELEMENTS

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The preparation and properties of the complex compounds of hexamethylenedibiguanide with Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(III) and Cr(III) have been described. Besides these usual complexes, a compound of Mn(IV) with this ligand has also been described.

Ethylenedibiguanide behaves as a quadridentate ligand. A large number of complex compounds of copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and silver(III) with ethylenedibiguanide have been described by Rây and co-workers (this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 291; 1944, 21, 47). Palladium(II), chromium(III) and cobalt(III) complexes of the same ligand have recently been characterised (Rây, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, in press). Ray and Rây (this *Journal*, 1958, 38, 595, 601) have also isolated well-defined Mn(IV) and Mn(III) complexes of ethylenedibiguanide.

In view of these fascinating observations on ethylenedibiguanide, it was thought interesting to investigate the complex-forming capacity of hexamethylenedibiguanide, $C_2N_2H_4-CH_2-(CH_2)_4-CH_2-C_2N_2H_4$, where the two biguanide residues will be, rather, widely separated.

Hexamethylenedibiguanide has been found to behave as a quadridentate ligand, forming characteristically coloured complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II), Cr(III) and Co(III). Like ethylenedibiguanide, the complexes of Cr(III) and Co(III) contain two atoms of the metal along with three molecules of the ligand, thus giving rise to a binuclear complex with a molecule of the dibiguanide functioning as a bridge between the two metal atoms. A complex Mn(IV) base of this ligand has also been isolated. This, however, is less stable than the corresponding ethylenedibiguanide complex and gives a rather low magnetic moment value ($\mu_s = 2.83$) as compared to the theoretical value of $3.87\mu_s$ for quadrivalent manganese. This value, however, is of the same order as found by Ray and Rây (*loc. cit.*) for a number of such Mn(IV) complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hexamethylenedibiguanide Acid Sulphate.—Hexamethylenediamine (12 g., 72% soln.), dicyandiamide (16 g.) and water (100 c.c.) were refluxed for half an hour. An aqueous solution of copper sulphate (10 g.) was added to the mixture in small portions at a time and the mixture refluxed for a total period of 3 hours. The rose-violet crystals, that separated, were filtered, dissolved in H_2SO_4 (dil.) and decomposed with H_2S . The filtrate from CuS was concentrated (50 c.c.) on the water-bath, cooled and treated with alcohol (150 c.c.). The colorless crystals of the hexamethylenedibiguanide acid sulphate were filtered and purified by recrystallisation from hot water, yield 16-18 g. {Found: SO_4 , 38.26; N, 27.89; H_2O , 3.15. $(C_{10}H_{24}N_{10})_2H_2SO_4 \cdot H_2O$ requires SO_4 , 38.55; N, 28.11; H_2O , 3.61%}.

1. *Copper-hexamethylenedibiguanidinium Hydroxide*.—A solution of hexamethylenedibiguanide sulphate (2.8 g.) was made strongly alkaline (NaOH) and to this was added dropwise an ammoniacal copper sulphate (1.25 g.) solution, when a light rose-violet product was precipitated. The mixture was digested on the water-bath, till the washed precipitate was free of sulphate. It was finally washed with alcohol and dried over KOH. The substance has a tendency to soften on the water-bath, but slowly becomes crystalline with time. It forms an anhydrobase at 130°. { Found: Cu, 15.83; N, 35.00; H₂O, 13.40. [Cu(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)](OH)₂·H₂O requires Cu, 15.90; N, 35.04; H₂O, 13.52% }.

2. The *sulphate* was obtained as a rose-violet precipitate by treating a solution of hexamethylenedibiguanide sulphate (2.8 g.) with an ammoniacal solution of copper sulphate (1.25 g.). The product was washed and dried as usual. { Found: Cu, 12.58; SO₄, 18.81; N, 27.65; H₂O, 13.26. [Cu(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)]SO₄·4H₂O requires Cu, 12.32; SO₄, 18.63; N, 27.16; H₂O, 13.96% }.

3. The *chloride* was obtained as a rose-red crystalline mass by digesting the complex base with ammonium chloride solution on the water-bath till the evolution of ammonia had ceased. { Found: Cu, 12.92; Cl, 14.20. [Cu(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)]Cl₂·4H₂O requires Cu, 12.95; Cl, 14.48% }.

4. The *acetate* was obtained by the action of ammonium acetate on the complex base. { Found: Cu, 11.04; N, 24.80; H₂O, 18.10. [Cu(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)](CH₃COO)₂·6H₂O requires Cu, 11.08; N, 24.40; H₂O, 18.83% }.

5. *Nickel-hexamethylenedibiguanidinium Hydroxide*.—A strongly alkaline solution of hexamethylenedibiguanide sulphate (2.8 g.), mixed with a solution of nickel sulphate (1.2 g.), was digested on the water-bath for several hours. The yellow-coloured precipitate was filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol and finally dried over KOH. The substance liberates ammonia from ammonium salts. { Found: Ni, 15.90; N, 36.90; H₂O, 9.0. [Ni(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)](OH)₂ requires Ni, 15.59; N, 37.16; H₂O, 9.50% }.

6. The *sulphate* was obtained by digesting the complex base with ammonium sulphate. { Found: Ni, 11.43; SO₄, 18.56; N, 27.65. [Ni(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)]SO₄·4H₂O requires Ni, 11.50; SO₄, 18.80; N, 27.40% }.

7. The *chloride* was prepared by the action of ammonium chloride on the complex base. { Found: Ni, 11.80; Cl, 14.67; N, 29.40. [Ni(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)]Cl₂·4H₂O requires Ni, 12.09; Cl, 14.62; N, 28.83% }.

8. *Di-cobaltic (III)-tris-hexamethylenedibiguanidinium Hydroxide*.—A solution of hexamethylenedibiguanide sulphate (5 g.) in water (200 c.c.) was made strongly alkaline with NaOH solution. The mixture was heated on the water-bath. As ammonia was given off, the complex base separated as a soft mass. This was cooled and filtered after 1½ hours. The product was washed as usual and dried over KOH. It forms dark red crystals, insoluble in water and alcohol. The substance becomes an anhydrobase by losing all its water at 110°. { Found: Co, 10.58; N, 37.67; H₂O, 11.40. [Co₂(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)₃](OH)₆·H₂O requires Co, 10.81; N, 38.52; H₂O, 11.56% }.

9. *Di-chromium (III)-tris-hexamethylenedibiguanidinium Hydroxide*.—A solution of hexamethylenedibiguanide sulphate (4 g. in 200 c.c. water) was made strongly alkaline

with NaOH solution and warmed on the water-bath. To this was added dropwise with constant stirring a solution of chrome alum (2 g.), taking care that all the chromium combined to give a red solution before any fresh addition was made. The dark red solution soon deposited a red-violet flocky mass. After half an hour of digestion, the mixture was cooled in ice with occasional scratching of the sides of the beaker, when the flocky mass changed to a crystalline product. The rose-violet crystals were filtered, washed first with water, then with alcohol and finally dried over KOH { Found: Cr, 9.54; N, 38.41; H₂O, 12.10. [Cr₂(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)₂].(OH)₂. 1.5 H₂O requires Cr, 9.58; N, 38.70; H₂O, 12.44% }.

The substance forms an anhydrobase at 120° by losing all water.

10. *Di-hydroxo-manganese (IV)-hexamethylenedibiguanidinium Hydroxide*.—Hexamethylenedibiguanide sulphate (5 g.) was dissolved in water (70 c.c.) containing sodium hydroxide (4 g.). The solution was cooled and then treated with a strong solution of potassium permanganate (0.4 g. in 30 c.c. water). The permanganate was first reduced to the green manganate and in course of 20 minutes, dark red crystals of the manganese complex separated out. After cooling for another half hour, the compound was filtered through a sintered glass Gooch crucible and washed with cold water. The product was dried in vacuum over CaCl₂. The substance forms dark red crystals, insoluble in water. It oxidises ferrous ion to ferric ion and liberates iodine from KI in acid solution. The substance decomposes on heating at 70°. { Found: O (active), 3.54; Mn, 12.20; N, 31.35. [Mn^{IV}(C₁₀H₂₄N₁₀)₂](OH)₂.2H₂O requires O (active), 3.61; Mn, 12.45; N, 31.74% }.

Magnetic Measurement: $\chi_g = 6.882 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 3049 \times 10^{-6}$; χ_x (corr.) = 3279×10^{-6} ; $\mu_s = 2.826$ (29.2°).

Author's grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây for his valuable suggestions.